

Appendix K: Additional figures for the JWST fitting results

Here we provide supplementary figures for the overall fittings of the COM fingerprint range (6.8–8.8 μm) in the JWST/MIRI-MRS spectrum of B1-c. Figure K.1 shows the best-fit lab spectra as in Fig. 7 but in a step-by-step form. Figure K.2 shows the corner plot of the MCMC fitting introduced in Sect. 4.2.4.

Fig. K.1: Same as Fig. 7 but displays the best fits species by species.

Fig. K.2: Corner plot of the MCMC fitting. Nine out of 12 candidate species are considered. The dashed lines in the histograms indicate the 16%, 50%, and 84% quantiles from left to right.

Appendix L: Additional table

Table L.1 lists the rotational transitions of the detected species reported in Table 1 covered in our ALMA Band 7 data (Sect. 2.1). Only those transitions that are used in the LTE fittings are listed.

Table L.1: Rotational transitions of the detected gas-phase molecules in the ALMA spectra.

Species (Database)	Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
CH₃OH , vt=0-2 (CDMS)	9 1 8 1 – 8 2 6 2	333864.722	125.52	8.04(-7)	★
	21 5 17 4 – 22 4 19 4	334326.177	964.39	1.99(-5)	★
	3 0 3 4 – 2 1 2 4	334426.571	314.47	5.55(-5)	†
	22 3 19 4 – 22 2 20 4	334626.849	1001.32	3.55(-5)	★
	25 3 23 5 – 24 2 23 5	334679.524	1073.85	1.46(-4)	†
	2 2 1 0 – 3 1 2 0	335133.570	44.67	2.69(-5)	†
	28 8 21 4 – 28 7 21 4	335205.794	1534.70	2.14(-4)	★
	7 1 7 0 – 6 1 6 0	335582.017	78.97	1.63(-4)	†
	14 7 7 0 – 15 6 9 0	336438.224	488.22	3.61(-5)	†
	14 7 8 0 – 15 6 10 0	336438.224	488.22	3.61(-5)	†
	7 1 7 6 – 6 1 6 6	336605.889	747.41	1.64(-4)	†
	27 9 18 0 – 26 6 21 3	336646.204	1293.65	2.29(-5)	
	27 9 19 0 – 26 6 20 3	336646.533	1293.65	2.29(-5)	
	7 6 1 6 – 6 6 0 6	336970.183	1022.71	4.57(-5)	
	7 6 2 6 – 6 6 1 6	336970.183	1022.71	4.57(-5)	
	7 3 4 8 – 6 3 3 8	337021.917	979.71	1.36(-4)	†
	7 2 6 6 – 6 2 5 6	337029.573	941.38	1.55(-4)	†
	7 2 5 6 – 6 2 4 6	337029.662	941.38	1.55(-4)	
	27 9 19 2 – 28 8 21 2	345318.303	1278.18	5.97(-5)	
	16 1 15 0 – 15 2 14 0	345903.916	332.65	1.04(-4)	†
18 3 15 2 – 17 4 14 2	345919.260	459.43	7.29(-5)	†	
19 3 16 4 – 19 2 17 4	347445.285	856.25	4.04(-5)		
¹³ CH ₃ OH, vt=0-1 (CDMS)	12 1 11 -0 – 12 0 12 +0	335560.207	192.66	4.04(-4)	†
	14 1 13 -0 – 14 0 14 +0	347188.283	254.25	4.36(-4)	†
CH₃¹⁸OH , v=0-2 (CDMS)	4 0 4 1 – 3 1 3 1	336100.324	35.09	7.42(-5)	*
	11 6 6 2 – 12 5 8 2	345858.184	326.94	3.54(-5)	
CH₂DOH (JPL)	19 8 11 2 – 20 7 14 2	333835.968	672.13	1.06(-5)	
	19 8 12 2 – 20 7 13 2	333835.968	672.13	1.06(-5)	
	16 2 15 0 – 16 1 16 0	333966.537	306.68	1.59(-4)	†
	20 3 17 1 – 20 2 18 1	334615.482	494.74	1.40(-5)	
	16 2 15 2 – 16 1 15 1	334683.954	326.58	1.09(-4)	†
	13 0 13 1 – 12 1 11 2	334900.931	207.26	2.69(-5)	
	23 0 23 0 – 22 1 21 2	335102.203	583.84	3.71(-5)	
	18 5 13 0 – 18 4 15 2	335103.631	464.26	2.80(-5)	
	18 5 14 0 – 18 4 14 2	335116.209	464.26	2.80(-5)	
	19 2 17 0 – 18 3 16 1	335578.757	427.23	1.50(-5)	
	20 3 18 2 – 19 4 15 2	336131.672	504.96	2.04(-5)	
	21 8 13 2 – 22 7 15 1	336973.378	759.76	2.43(-5)	
	21 8 14 2 – 22 7 16 1	336973.383	759.76	2.43(-5)	
	16 2 14 0 – 15 3 13 0	345398.904	310.21	5.83(-5)	
	23 4 19 1 – 23 3 21 2	345701.510	662.81	1.34(-4)	★
	3 2 1 1 – 2 1 2 1	345718.718	39.44	4.23(-5)	
	19 1 19 1 – 18 2 17 2	345820.793	418.03	2.94(-5)	★
	22 4 19 1 – 22 3 19 2	345850.485	613.62	1.29(-4)	★
	8 2 6 2 – 7 3 4 0	346031.073	112.62	1.76(-6)	
	20 4 16 1 – 19 5 15 0	346042.562	521.63	1.32(-5)	
	20 4 17 1 – 19 5 14 0	346062.966	521.63	1.32(-5)	
	21 4 18 1 – 21 3 18 2	346419.064	566.56	1.30(-4)	★
	7 5 2 2 – 8 4 5 2	346434.692	175.80	7.74(-6)	
	7 5 3 2 – 8 4 4 2	346434.725	175.80	7.74(-6)	
	20 4 16 1 – 20 3 18 2	347222.992	521.63	1.32(-4)	
	19 4 16 1 – 19 3 16 2	347371.167	478.84	1.30(-4)	
	20 7 14 1 – 21 6 15 0	347467.621	651.60	2.02(-5)	
20 7 13 1 – 21 6 16 0	347468.666	651.60	2.02(-5)		

Table L.1: continued.

Species (Database)	Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
CH₃CHO (JPL)	18 1 18 1 – 17 1 17 1	333941.356	155.22	1.28(-3)	B1-c†
	18 1 18 0 – 17 1 17 0	333959.754	155.15	1.28(-3)	B1-c†
	18 1 18 3 – 17 1 17 3	334341.281	361.72	1.30(-3)	★
	17 2 15 3 – 16 2 14 3	334637.404	357.95	1.28(-3)	
	17 4 14 7 – 16 4 13 7	334665.820	548.85	1.18(-3)	
	25 4 22 1 – 25 3 23 1	334756.255	337.33	1.30(-4)	
	17 2 15 2 – 16 2 14 2	334904.591	152.63	1.28(-3)	B1-c†
	17 2 15 0 – 16 2 14 0	334931.415	152.61	1.28(-3)	B1-c†
	18 1 18 4 – 17 1 17 4	334980.853	359.89	1.28(-3)	★
	18 0 18 2 – 17 0 17 2	335318.109	154.93	1.30(-3)	B1-c†
	18 0 18 0 – 17 0 17 0	335358.722	154.85	1.29(-3)	B1-c†
	18 0 18 3 – 17 0 17 3	335382.461	361.48	1.31(-3)	★
	17 6 12 7 – 16 6 11 7	335560.509	591.60	1.10(-3)	
	17 2 15 6 – 16 2 14 6	336127.216	529.83	1.25(-3)	
	18 1 17 8 – 17 1 16 8	345992.130	545.09	1.38(-3)	
	18 2 17 4 – 17 2 16 4	346065.350	371.35	1.40(-3)	
	18 7 11 5 – 17 7 10 5	346451.075	474.02	1.22(-3)	★
	18 6 12 5 – 17 6 11 5	346591.092	445.29	1.28(-3)	
	18 7 12 0 – 17 7 11 0	346957.556	268.61	1.22(-3)	B1-c†
	18 7 11 0 – 17 7 10 0	346957.558	268.61	1.22(-3)	B1-c†
	18 7 12 1 – 17 7 11 1	346995.532	268.57	1.22(-3)	
	18 7 11 6 – 17 7 10 6	346999.913	646.35	1.22(-3)	★
	18 7 12 6 – 17 7 11 6	346999.941	646.35	1.22(-3)	★
	18 6 13 1 – 17 6 12 1	347132.686	239.32	1.28(-3)	
	18 4 14 8 – 17 4 13 8	347155.125	573.93	1.37(-3)	
	9 4 6 4 – 9 3 7 4	347155.775	282.78	1.20(-4)	
	19 0 19 0 – 18 1 18 0	347169.520	171.81	2.09(-4)	
	18 4 14 5 – 17 4 13 5	347182.413	400.38	1.37(-3)	★
	18 5 13 5 – 17 5 12 5	347216.798	420.44	1.33(-3)	
	19 0 19 2 – 18 1 18 1	347240.396	171.89	2.08(-4)	
	18 5 14 4 – 17 5 13 4	347251.822	419.67	1.33(-3)	
	18 5 14 0 – 17 5 13 0	347288.264	214.70	1.33(-3)	
18 5 13 0 – 17 5 12 0	347294.873	214.70	1.33(-3)		
18 5 13 2 – 17 5 12 2	347345.710	214.64	1.33(-3)		
18 5 14 1 – 17 5 13 1	347349.278	214.61	1.33(-3)		
18 7 12 3 – 17 7 11 3	347459.353	473.15	1.22(-3)	★	
18 7 11 3 – 17 7 10 3	347459.355	473.15	1.22(-3)	★	
18 3 16 0 – 17 3 15 0	347519.185	178.75	1.41(-3)	B1-c†	
18 3 16 1 – 17 3 15 1	347563.334	178.71	1.41(-3)	B1-c†	
C₂H₅OH, v=0 (CDMS)	25 7 19 2 – 25 6 20 2	334110.890	334.91	2.39(-4)	
	44 7 38 2 – 44 6 39 2	334543.992	897.54	2.64(-4)	
	24 7 17 2 – 24 6 18 2	334602.657	313.84	2.37(-4)	
	12 5 7 0 – 11 4 7 1	334742.442	152.19	1.27(-4)	
	20 1 19 2 – 19 2 18 2	334769.072	178.68	2.75(-4)	★
	12 5 8 0 – 11 4 8 1	334811.021	152.19	1.27(-4)	
	24 7 18 2 – 24 6 19 2	334911.577	313.83	2.38(-4)	
	23 7 16 2 – 23 6 17 2	335440.539	293.61	2.36(-4)	
	23 7 17 2 – 23 6 18 2	335630.619	293.61	2.36(-4)	
	13 3 11 2 – 12 2 10 2	335949.651	87.87	1.43(-4)	
	19 3 16 1 – 18 3 15 1	336572.411	232.34	3.14(-4)	
	19 2 18 2 – 18 1 17 2	336626.401	162.61	2.71(-4)	
	21 1 21 1 – 20 1 20 1	345295.355	246.22	3.67(-4)	
	21 0 21 0 – 20 0 20 0	345333.442	241.54	3.72(-4)	
	20 13 7 1 – 19 13 6 1	345966.686	443.28	2.10(-4)	
	20 13 8 1 – 19 13 7 1	345966.686	443.28	2.10(-4)	
	20 14 6 1 – 19 14 5 1	345970.743	476.27	1.85(-4)	
	20 14 7 1 – 19 14 6 1	345970.743	476.27	1.85(-4)	
	20 12 8 1 – 19 12 7 1	345981.237	412.70	2.33(-4)	
	20 12 9 1 – 19 12 8 1	345981.237	412.70	2.33(-4)	

Table L.1: continued.

Species (Database)	Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
	20 11 9 1 – 19 11 8 1	346017.212	384.56	2.55(-4)	★
	20 11 10 1 – 19 11 9 1	346017.212	384.56	2.55(-4)	★
	20 10 10 1 – 19 10 9 1	346085.563	358.85	2.74(-4)	★
	20 10 11 1 – 19 10 10 1	346085.563	358.85	2.74(-4)	★
	20 10 10 0 – 19 10 9 0	346424.583	353.45	2.91(-4)	★
	20 10 11 0 – 19 10 10 0	346424.583	353.45	2.91(-4)	★
	20 9 12 0 – 19 9 11 0	346505.347	330.25	3.09(-4)	
	20 9 11 0 – 19 9 10 0	346505.347	330.25	3.09(-4)	
	20 7 14 1 – 19 7 13 1	346565.082	296.37	3.22(-4)	
	20 7 13 1 – 19 7 12 1	346565.398	296.37	3.22(-4)	
	20 17 3 0 – 19 17 2 0	346610.251	584.43	1.12(-4)	
	20 17 4 0 – 19 17 3 0	346610.251	584.43	1.12(-4)	
	20 8 13 0 – 19 8 12 0	346620.325	309.51	3.26(-4)	★
	20 8 12 0 – 19 8 11 0	346620.333	309.51	3.26(-4)	★
	20 6 14 1 – 19 6 13 1	346938.874	280.48	3.34(-4)	
	21 0 21 2 – 20 1 20 2	346962.603	185.84	4.45(-4)	★
	20 6 15 0 – 19 6 14 0	347147.209	275.46	3.55(-4)	
	20 6 14 0 – 19 6 13 0	347157.997	275.46	3.55(-4)	
	14 3 12 2 – 13 2 11 2	347351.089	99.66	1.56(-4)	
	21 1 21 2 – 20 0 20 2	347445.568	185.85	4.47(-4)	
	20 5 16 1 – 19 5 15 1	347473.561	267.09	3.45(-4)	
CH₃OCH₃, v=0 (CDMS)	37 7 30 0 – 37 6 31 0	347340.892	710.39	2.38(-4)	*
	37 7 30 1 – 37 6 31 1	347342.977	710.39	2.38(-4)	*
	37 7 30 5 – 37 6 31 5	347345.059	710.39	2.38(-4)	*
	37 7 30 3 – 37 6 31 3	347345.066	710.39	2.38(-4)	*
CH₃OCHO (JPL)	15 6 10 1 – 14 5 9 2	333972.824	94.90	2.42(-5)	
	27 11 16 2 – 26 11 15 2	334017.031	303.76	4.74(-4)	★
	27 11 17 0 – 26 11 16 0	334031.781	303.76	4.74(-4)	†
	27 11 16 0 – 26 11 15 0	334031.781	303.76	4.74(-4)	
	27 11 17 1 – 26 11 16 1	334044.362	303.76	4.74(-4)	
	27 8 20 3 – 26 8 19 3	334074.073	453.00	5.18(-4)	
	15 6 10 0 – 14 5 9 0	334109.114	94.90	3.79(-5)	
	27 6 22 4 – 26 6 21 4	334138.972	435.17	5.39(-4)	
	29 5 24 2 – 28 6 23 1	334179.438	282.10	2.99(-5)	
	26 5 21 5 – 25 5 20 5	334228.598	416.22	5.48(-4)	★
	29 5 24 0 – 28 6 23 0	334235.866	282.10	2.99(-5)	★
	27 8 19 5 – 26 8 18 5	334660.939	453.20	5.11(-4)	
	27 8 19 3 – 26 8 18 3	334700.891	453.07	5.21(-4)	★
	27 10 17 2 – 26 10 16 2	334850.947	290.09	4.93(-4)	
	27 10 18 0 – 26 10 17 0	334867.014	290.09	4.94(-4)	★
	27 10 17 0 – 26 10 16 0	334872.791	290.09	4.94(-4)	★
	27 10 18 1 – 26 10 17 1	334877.566	290.08	4.93(-4)	★
	27 7 21 3 – 26 7 20 3	335015.896	443.53	5.33(-4)	★
	27 8 20 4 – 26 8 19 4	335391.536	453.05	5.14(-4)	
	27 9 19 0 – 26 9 18 0	336028.165	277.85	5.14(-4)	
	27 9 19 1 – 26 9 18 1	336032.357	277.85	4.90(-4)	
	27 9 18 2 – 26 9 17 2	336086.182	277.86	4.90(-4)	
	27 9 18 0 – 26 9 17 0	336111.324	277.86	5.15(-4)	
	9 9 0 0 – 8 8 1 0	345718.662	80.32	9.86(-5)	
	9 9 1 0 – 8 8 0 0	345718.662	80.32	9.86(-5)	
	28 6 23 4 – 27 6 22 4	345828.557	451.76	5.99(-4)	
	28 12 16 2 – 27 12 15 2	345974.664	335.44	5.16(-4)	
	28 12 17 0 – 27 12 16 0	345985.381	335.44	5.16(-4)	
	28 12 16 0 – 27 12 15 0	345985.381	335.44	5.16(-4)	
	28 12 17 1 – 27 12 16 1	346001.616	335.43	5.16(-4)	★
	28 9 20 4 – 27 9 19 4	346564.463	480.56	5.69(-4)	
	27 6 21 3 – 26 6 20 3	346580.244	437.64	6.04(-4)	
	27 5 22 2 – 26 5 21 2	347478.251	247.25	6.14(-4)	†
	27 5 22 0 – 26 5 21 0	347493.965	247.26	6.14(-4)	†

Table L.1: continued.

Species (Database)	Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
CH₂OHCHO , $v=0$ (CDMS)	37 8 29 0 – 36 9 28 0	334382.061	439.41	1.83(-4)	*
	35 14 21 0 – 35 13 22 0	334587.394	469.56	5.85(-4)	
	35 14 22 0 – 35 13 23 0	334588.479	469.56	5.85(-4)	
	50 7 43 0 – 50 6 44 0	334859.254	750.32	4.85(-4)	
	17 6 11 0 – 16 5 12 0	335097.924	107.27	3.89(-4)	
	34 14 20 0 – 34 13 21 0	335441.062	450.00	5.81(-4)	
	34 14 21 0 – 34 13 22 0	335441.575	450.00	5.81(-4)	
	30 5 25 0 – 29 6 24 0	335456.548	282.11	4.31(-4)	
	47 15 32 0 – 47 14 33 0	346572.448	765.89	7.26(-4)	*
18 6 12 0 – 17 5 13 0	347445.973	117.44	4.02(-4)		
<i>a</i>-(CH₂OH)₂ (CDMS)	32 18 14 1 – 31 18 13 0	334043.836	418.76	6.24(-4)	
	32 18 15 1 – 31 18 14 0	334043.836	418.76	6.24(-4)	
	32 17 15 1 – 31 17 14 0	334058.781	401.61	6.55(-4)	
	32 17 16 1 – 31 17 15 0	334058.781	401.61	6.56(-4)	
	32 19 13 1 – 31 19 12 0	334059.121	436.89	5.91(-4)	
	32 19 14 1 – 31 19 13 0	334059.121	436.89	5.91(-4)	
	32 20 12 1 – 31 20 11 0	334100.228	456.00	5.57(-4)	
	32 20 13 1 – 31 20 12 0	334100.228	456.00	5.57(-4)	
	32 16 16 1 – 31 16 15 0	334109.885	385.45	6.85(-4)	
	32 16 17 1 – 31 16 16 0	334109.885	385.45	6.85(-4)	
	36 2 35 0 – 35 2 34 1	334141.377	310.88	9.15(-4)	†
	36 1 35 0 – 35 1 34 1	334141.397	310.88	9.15(-4)	†
	32 21 11 1 – 31 21 10 0	334163.829	476.08	5.20(-4)	
	32 21 12 1 – 31 21 11 0	334163.829	476.08	5.21(-4)	
	33 10 24 0 – 32 10 23 1	334193.102	325.62	8.29(-4)	
	32 15 17 1 – 31 15 16 0	334205.280	370.28	7.13(-4)	★
	32 15 18 1 – 31 15 17 0	334205.280	370.28	7.14(-4)	★
	33 10 23 0 – 32 10 22 1	334211.959	325.62	8.30(-4)	
	32 22 10 1 – 31 22 9 0	334247.377	497.14	4.82(-4)	
	32 22 11 1 – 31 22 10 0	334247.377	497.14	4.82(-4)	
	32 23 9 1 – 31 23 8 0	334348.904	519.17	4.43(-4)	
	32 23 10 1 – 31 23 9 0	334348.904	519.17	4.43(-4)	
	32 14 18 1 – 31 14 17 0	334356.392	356.11	7.40(-4)	★
	32 14 19 1 – 31 14 18 0	334356.392	356.11	7.40(-4)	★
	32 24 8 1 – 31 24 7 0	334466.874	542.17	4.01(-4)	
	32 24 9 1 – 31 24 8 0	334466.874	542.17	4.01(-4)	
	32 6 26 0 – 31 6 25 1	334555.253	282.34	8.95(-4)	
	32 13 20 1 – 31 13 19 0	334579.759	342.94	7.66(-4)	
	32 13 19 1 – 31 13 18 0	334579.760	342.94	7.66(-4)	
	36 0 36 0 – 35 1 35 0	334804.512	300.16	1.85(-4)	
	36 1 36 0 – 35 0 35 0	334804.513	300.16	1.85(-4)	
	36 0 36 1 – 35 1 35 1	334821.007	300.51	1.85(-4)	
	36 1 36 1 – 35 0 35 1	334821.008	300.51	1.85(-4)	
	32 12 21 1 – 31 12 20 0	334900.249	330.78	7.91(-4)	
	32 12 20 1 – 31 12 19 0	334900.284	330.78	7.91(-4)	
	32 6 27 1 – 31 6 26 0	335030.116	279.36	9.34(-4)	
	33 9 25 0 – 32 9 24 1	335179.801	316.68	8.51(-4)	
	32 11 22 1 – 31 11 21 0	335356.975	319.65	8.15(-4)	
	32 11 21 1 – 31 11 20 0	335357.726	319.65	8.15(-4)	
	33 9 24 0 – 32 9 23 1	335396.713	316.71	8.53(-4)	
34 4 31 1 – 33 3 30 1	336053.816	297.13	1.33(-4)		
34 4 31 0 – 33 3 30 0	336054.127	296.80	1.12(-4)		
34 5 29 1 – 33 6 28 1	336608.832	311.78	3.62(-4)		
33 11 23 1 – 32 11 22 0	345737.011	335.95	9.00(-4)		
33 11 22 1 – 32 11 21 0	345738.443	335.95	9.01(-4)		
34 9 26 0 – 33 9 25 1	345812.719	333.57	9.36(-4)		
34 8 27 0 – 33 8 26 1	345832.886	325.79	5.43(-4)		
38 1 38 0 – 37 1 37 1	345912.524	333.62	1.02(-3)		
38 0 38 0 – 37 0 37 1	345912.524	333.62	1.02(-3)		

Table L.1: continued.

Species (Database)	Transition		Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
	34 7 28 0	– 33 7 27 1	346462.657	318.83	9.43(-4)	★
	33 10 24 1	– 32 10 23 0	346468.981	325.91	9.26(-4)	★
	33 10 23 1	– 32 10 22 0	346490.976	325.91	9.26(-4)	
	34 5 29 0	– 33 5 28 1	346630.908	311.52	1.07(-3)	
	36 4 33 0	– 35 4 32 1	347361.377	330.36	1.02(-3)	
	36 3 33 0	– 35 3 32 1	347377.705	330.36	1.01(-3)	★
	32 6 26 1	– 31 6 25 0	347387.171	282.65	9.81(-4)	
	33 9 25 1	– 32 9 24 0	347486.902	316.98	9.51(-4)	
	33 8 25 1	– 32 8 25 1	347596.647	309.41	1.23(-4)	
$g\text{-}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2$ (CDMS)	23 5 19 0	– 22 4 19 1	333807.874	147.69	1.88(-4)	
	31 17 14 1	– 31 16 16 0	333830.012	382.39	1.47(-4)	
	31 17 15 1	– 31 16 15 0	333830.012	382.39	1.47(-4)	
	30 17 13 1	– 30 16 15 0	333926.319	367.26	1.43(-4)	
	30 17 14 1	– 30 16 14 0	333926.319	367.26	1.43(-4)	
	32 5 27 1	– 31 5 26 0	334079.683	276.07	3.19(-4)	
	28 17 11 1	– 28 16 13 0	334088.087	338.47	1.35(-4)	
	28 17 12 1	– 28 16 12 0	334088.087	338.47	1.35(-4)	
	32 7 25 0	– 31 7 24 1	334098.077	284.34	3.31(-4)	
	34 3 31 1	– 33 4 30 1	334112.202	295.02	1.78(-4)	
	34 3 31 0	– 33 4 30 0	334120.029	294.96	3.08(-4)	
	27 17 10 1	– 27 16 12 0	334155.000	324.80	1.30(-4)	
	27 17 11 1	– 27 16 11 0	334155.000	324.80	1.30(-4)	
	20 7 13 1	– 19 6 13 0	334167.497	126.59	2.43(-4)	
	26 17 9 1	– 26 16 11 0	334213.515	311.63	1.25(-4)	
	26 17 10 1	– 26 16 10 0	334213.515	311.63	1.25(-4)	
	34 4 31 1	– 33 3 30 1	334253.644	295.03	3.07(-4)	
	34 4 31 0	– 33 3 30 0	334264.186	294.97	1.79(-4)	
	25 17 8 1	– 25 16 10 0	334264.285	298.94	1.19(-4)	
	25 17 9 1	– 25 16 9 0	334264.285	298.94	1.19(-4)	
	24 17 7 1	– 24 16 9 0	334307.936	286.74	1.12(-4)	
	24 17 8 1	– 24 16 8 0	334307.936	286.74	1.12(-4)	
	18 8 11 1	– 17 7 10 1	334320.081	114.67	1.86(-4)	
	18 8 10 1	– 17 7 11 1	334325.869	114.67	1.86(-4)	
	23 17 6 1	– 23 16 8 0	334345.068	275.03	1.04(-4)	
	23 17 7 1	– 23 16 7 0	334345.068	275.03	1.04(-4)	
	18 8 11 0	– 17 7 10 0	334354.965	114.62	1.88(-4)	
	18 8 10 0	– 17 7 11 0	334360.695	114.62	1.89(-4)	
	12 11 1 1	– 11 10 2 1	334506.538	96.91	3.56(-4)	★
	12 11 2 1	– 11 10 1 1	334506.538	96.91	3.56(-4)	★
	12 11 1 0	– 11 10 2 0	334538.884	96.86	3.56(-4)	★
	12 11 2 0	– 11 10 1 0	334538.884	96.86	3.56(-4)	★
	20 7 14 1	– 19 6 14 0	334562.201	126.58	2.05(-4)	
	16 9 8 1	– 15 8 7 1	334599.304	105.79	2.28(-4)	
	16 9 7 1	– 15 8 8 1	334599.324	105.79	2.28(-4)	
	14 10 4 1	– 13 9 5 1	334604.473	99.88	2.81(-4)	
	14 10 5 1	– 13 9 4 1	334604.473	99.88	2.81(-4)	
	16 9 8 0	– 15 8 7 0	334633.280	105.74	2.30(-4)	
	16 9 7 0	– 15 8 8 0	334633.300	105.74	2.30(-4)	
	14 10 4 0	– 13 9 5 0	334637.793	99.83	2.82(-4)	
	14 10 5 0	– 13 9 4 0	334637.793	99.83	2.82(-4)	
	36 0 36 1	– 35 0 35 0	334709.849	298.92	3.61(-4)	★
	36 1 36 1	– 35 1 35 0	334709.849	298.92	3.61(-4)	★
	33 20 13 0	– 32 20 12 1	334838.561	467.86	2.18(-4)	
	33 20 14 0	– 32 20 13 1	334838.561	467.86	2.18(-4)	
	33 21 12 0	– 32 21 11 1	334840.150	487.72	2.05(-4)	
	33 21 13 0	– 32 21 12 1	334840.150	487.72	2.05(-4)	
	33 19 14 0	– 32 19 13 1	334851.819	448.96	2.31(-4)	
	33 19 15 0	– 32 19 14 1	334851.819	448.96	2.31(-4)	
	33 22 11 0	– 32 22 10 1	334852.879	508.55	1.91(-4)	

Table L.1: continued.

Species (Database)	Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
	33 22 12 0 – 32 22 11 1	334852.879	508.55	1.91(-4)	
	33 18 15 0 – 32 18 14 1	334884.208	431.04	2.43(-4)	
	33 18 16 0 – 32 18 15 1	334884.208	431.04	2.43(-4)	
	33 17 16 0 – 32 17 15 1	334940.915	414.08	2.55(-4)	
	33 17 17 0 – 32 17 16 1	334940.915	414.08	2.55(-4)	
	22 6 17 1 – 21 5 17 0	334954.517	141.61	2.37(-4)	
	33 5 29 0 – 32 4 28 0	334987.470	286.45	3.98(-4)	
	33 16 17 0 – 32 16 16 1	335028.496	398.10	2.66(-4)	
	33 16 18 0 – 32 16 17 1	335028.496	398.10	2.66(-4)	
	33 15 18 0 – 32 15 17 1	335155.577	383.11	2.76(-4)	
	33 15 19 0 – 32 15 18 1	335155.577	383.11	2.76(-4)	
	23 4 20 0 – 22 3 20 1	335226.462	142.78	1.46(-4)	
	33 14 20 0 – 32 14 19 1	335333.954	369.09	2.86(-4)	
	33 14 19 0 – 32 14 18 1	335333.954	369.09	2.86(-4)	
	34 4 31 1 – 33 4 30 0	335422.139	295.03	2.84(-4)	★
	34 3 31 1 – 33 3 30 0	335459.569	295.02	4.14(-4)	
	18 8 10 1 – 17 7 10 0	335462.789	114.67	2.38(-4)	
	18 8 11 1 – 17 7 11 0	335467.703	114.67	2.37(-4)	
	36 6 30 1 – 35 7 29 1	335488.573	349.86	1.07(-4)	
	33 13 21 0 – 32 13 20 1	335580.432	356.08	2.96(-4)	
	33 13 20 0 – 32 13 19 1	335580.435	356.08	2.96(-4)	
	35 3 33 0 – 34 3 32 1	335588.334	302.57	3.60(-4)	
	35 2 33 0 – 34 2 32 1	335589.204	302.57	3.55(-4)	
	32 7 25 1 – 31 7 24 0	336072.528	284.39	3.32(-4)	
	33 22 11 1 – 32 22 10 0	336092.641	508.57	1.93(-4)	
	33 22 12 1 – 32 22 11 0	336092.641	508.57	1.93(-4)	
	33 20 13 1 – 32 20 12 0	336099.583	467.89	2.20(-4)	
	33 20 14 1 – 32 20 13 0	336099.583	467.89	2.20(-4)	
	33 23 10 1 – 32 23 9 0	336116.773	530.36	1.78(-4)	
	33 23 11 1 – 32 23 10 0	336116.773	530.36	1.78(-4)	
	33 15 18 1 – 32 15 17 0	336558.515	383.14	2.79(-4)	
	33 15 19 1 – 32 15 18 0	336558.515	383.14	2.79(-4)	
	23 4 20 1 – 22 2 20 1	337017.819	142.83	1.10(-4)	
	25 6 20 0 – 24 5 19 0	337038.379	177.09	1.09(-4)	
	34 15 19 0 – 33 15 18 1	345385.355	399.71	3.07(-4)	
	34 15 20 0 – 33 15 19 1	345385.355	399.71	3.07(-4)	
	13 11 2 1 – 12 10 2 0	345836.731	103.25	3.87(-4)	★
	13 11 3 1 – 12 10 3 0	345836.731	103.25	3.87(-4)	★
	17 9 8 1 – 16 8 8 0	345841.998	114.10	2.83(-4)	★
	17 9 9 1 – 16 8 9 0	345841.998	114.10	2.83(-4)	★
	34 13 22 0 – 33 13 21 1	345862.205	372.71	3.27(-4)	★
	34 13 21 0 – 33 13 20 1	345862.211	372.71	3.27(-4)	★
	15 10 5 1 – 14 9 5 0	345906.318	107.20	3.25(-4)	
	15 10 6 1 – 14 9 6 0	345906.318	107.20	3.25(-4)	
	36 2 34 1 – 35 3 33 1	345985.032	319.24	3.20(-4)	
	36 3 34 1 – 35 2 33 1	345986.658	319.24	3.23(-4)	
	36 2 34 0 – 35 3 33 0	345987.306	319.18	3.24(-4)	
	36 3 34 0 – 35 2 33 0	345988.992	319.18	3.21(-4)	
	34 17 17 1 – 33 17 16 0	346444.360	430.71	2.87(-4)	
	34 17 18 1 – 33 17 17 0	346444.360	430.71	2.87(-4)	
	24 3 21 1 – 23 2 21 0	346551.132	154.12	1.52(-4)	
	35 5 30 0 – 34 6 29 0	346551.443	326.48	1.29(-4)	
	35 5 30 1 – 34 6 29 1	346568.765	326.51	2.15(-4)	
	34 16 18 1 – 33 16 17 0	346577.753	414.74	2.98(-4)	
	34 16 19 1 – 33 16 18 0	346577.753	414.74	2.98(-4)	
	29 6 24 1 – 28 5 23 1	346986.538	231.40	1.13(-4)	
	34 14 21 1 – 33 14 20 0	346993.104	385.75	3.20(-4)	
	34 14 20 1 – 33 14 19 0	346993.104	385.75	3.20(-4)	
	36 3 34 1 – 35 3 33 0	347254.922	319.24	3.93(-4)	

Table L.1: continued.

Species (Database)	Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_{up} (K)	A_{ij} (s^{-1}) $a(b) = a \times 10^b$	Note
	36 2 34 1 – 35 2 33 0	347255.462	319.24	3.97(-4)	
	34 13 22 1 – 33 13 21 0	347306.553	372.75	3.30(-4)	
	34 13 21 1 – 33 13 20 0	347306.559	372.75	3.30(-4)	
	34 10 25 0 – 33 10 24 1	347502.019	339.86	3.56(-4)	
	37 2 36 0 – 36 2 35 1	347507.368	326.07	4.01(-4)	
	37 1 36 0 – 36 1 35 1	347507.368	326.07	4.01(-4)	
	34 10 24 0 – 33 10 23 1	347535.163	339.86	3.56(-4)	
t-HCOOH (CDMS)	35 4 31 – 35 3 32	334247.840	739.34	7.49(-6)	
	15 2 14 – 14 2 13	334265.833	141.58	4.17(-4)	†
H₂CCO (CDMS)	17 1 16 – 16 1 15	346600.451	162.79	4.74(-4)	
CH₂DCN (CDMS)	20 1 20 – 19 1 19	345685.375	179.63	3.60(-3)	
	20 7 13 – 19 7 12	346968.947	438.92	3.20(-3)	
	20 7 14 – 19 7 13	346968.947	438.92	3.20(-3)	
	20 0 20 – 19 0 19	347043.458	174.96	3.65(-3)	★
	20 6 14 – 19 6 13	347044.649	368.95	3.32(-3)	★
	20 6 15 – 19 6 14	347044.649	368.95	3.32(-3)	★
	20 5 15 – 19 5 14	347110.032	309.72	3.42(-3)	★
	20 5 16 – 19 5 15	347110.032	309.72	3.42(-3)	★
	20 4 17 – 19 4 16	347166.409	261.24	3.50(-3)	★
	20 4 16 – 19 4 15	347166.421	261.24	3.50(-3)	★
	20 2 19 – 19 2 18	347188.253	196.56	3.61(-3)	
	20 3 18 – 19 3 17	347216.880	223.53	3.57(-3)	
	20 3 17 – 19 3 16	347219.365	223.53	3.57(-3)	
	20 2 18 – 19 2 17	347388.249	196.62	3.62(-3)	
C₂H₅CN , $v=0$ (CDMS)	37 5 32 – 36 5 31	333921.554	330.94	3.11(-3)	
	39 3 37 – 38 3 36	345921.198	344.46	3.50(-3)	
	38 3 35 – 37 3 34	346983.834	333.42	3.53(-3)	
NH₂CHO (CDMS)	16 2 15 – 15 2 14	336136.877	149.67	2.76(-3)	
	16 1 15 – 15 1 14	345326.688	145.16	3.02(-3)	

Note:

★: for the robustly detected species, key transitions that are used to constrain the column densities and excitation temperatures; must be optically thin and unblended.

*: for the tentatively detected species, key transitions that are used to estimate upper limits of column densities.

†: transitions that are (expected to be) optically thick and not considered in the fitting.